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Subtype-specific expression of SLIT, ROBO, NETRIN, EPHRIN, PLEXIN B and SEMAPHORIN in breast cancer.

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Guidance receptors have been implicated in processes outside of axon guidance in the central nervous system, like cancer. In breast cancer, we did not find significant over-expression of specific SLIT, ROBO or Ephrin genes, surprisingly. However, we did find subtype specific Semaphorin expression, with enrichment of Semaphorin 4B (*SEMA4B*) in the luminal A subtype in the primary tumor.